

**Arhiv za higijenu rada i
toksikologiju**

**Archives of Industrial
Hygiene and Toxicology**

2022;73(Suppl. 1)

**Abstracts of the 4th International Congress on
Food Safety and Quality
“One Health”**

9-12 November 2022

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Cover page: *Dubrovnik*

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Organised by

Andrija Štampar Teaching Institute of Public Health

South East European Network for Food Safety and Quality Control – SEEN-FSQC

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Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb
Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb
Institute of Health and Food Safety, Zenica, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Under the auspices of:

City of Zagreb
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia
Ministry of Health of the Republic of Croatia
Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Croatia
Croatian Agency for Agriculture and Food
Croatian Accreditation Agency
State Office for Metrology
Croatian Chamber of Economy
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4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality ONE HEALTH

November 9th-12th, 2022 | Dubrovnik, Croatia

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Dear colleagues, dear friends,

It is my great honour and pleasure to invite you on behalf of the Organising and Scientific Committee to participate in the 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality under the slogan “One Health”, which will be held in Dubrovnik, from 9 to 12 November 2022.

The International Congress on Food Safety and Quality will again be held under the auspices of the competent authorities and institutions and is organised by the Andrija Štampar Teaching Institute of Public Health, the Croatian Metrology Society, and the Southeast European Food Quality and Safety Control Network (SEEN-FSQC). The co-organisers are the Faculty of Agriculture and the Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, the University of Zagreb, the Institute for Health and Food Safety Zenica, and the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, in cooperation with other eminent institutions from the country and abroad.

Thanks to the extremely important topics and the esteemed experts who shared their knowledge and experiences with us at the first three Congresses on Food Safety and Quality, we were all happy to see

truly great interest: the Congresses New Achievements and Future Challenges in 2017, Food Life Cycle in 2018, and Food, Health and Climate Change in 2020 were attended by nearly 1,000 participants, while numerous guest speakers from the country and the world presented their colourful presentations in the form of exceptional plenary lectures, excellent oral presentations, satellite symposia, workshops, and posters. On the wings of these successes, our goal is to organise an even more significant, distinctive, and educational 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality.

We will present the significant experiences of domestic and foreign experts in the field of food counterfeiting, protection of the origin and geographical origin of food, and new, exact analytical achievements in this field.

Food safety and quality, determination of food origin and geographical origin, adulteration of food and its impact on consumer health, as well as the impact of climate change on farming and quality are all topics of crucial significance and impose a shared responsibility on all stakeholders in the food production chain. These are primarily countries, producers, distributors, consumers, but also the media, which are responsible for accurately reporting current topics to the public, including this very relevant issue.

Given that our common task is not only to protect, but also to improve the health of each of our residents, by organising the 4th International Congress “One Health” we also want to continue to raise awareness of this important topic in the profession.

Thank you for your response.

Sincerely,
Prof Branko Kolarić, MD, PhD
Congress President

Organic UV-filters in cosmetic products: determination and risk assessment

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Usage of sun-protection cosmetic products that contain UV-filters is on the rise due to climate changes and increased summer UV-indices. Therefore, a collection of cosmetic products comprising 79 samples from the Serbian market was subjected to high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)-UV analysis, using a validated method with seven UV-filters in its scope, a compliance check related to the Cosmetics Regulation (1223/2009), and a risk assessment using a Margin of safety (MOS) approach. The amount of UV-filters was in line with the Regulation. The risk assessment showed that phenylbenzimidazole sulfonic acid, ethylhexyl salicylate, butyl methoxydibenzoylmethane, ethylhexyl methoxycinnamate, and octocrylene in sun-protection products did not pose a risk for consumers. Conversely, benzophenone-3 was a cause of a concern in 2 of the 13 analysed sun-protection products for children (MOS below 100). In case of homosalate, the risk assessment revealed a huge disagreement between the regulated maximum concentration and the resulting MOS. More precisely, the substantially reduced NOAEL, established by the EU Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety in 2021, led to an unacceptable MOS below 10. The MOS for analysed sun-protection products for adults ranged 6-24 (16 out of 31 products), whereas in children the MOS depended on age, with an overall range of 5-12 (4 out of 13 products). Risk from any of the UV-filters in adults' face creams, tinted creams, and liquid powders, as well as lip balms was negligible. However, an aggregate exposure from multiple products, with sun-protection products included, poses a risk from homosalates. Therefore, a recommendation for the reduction of homosalate concentration should be seriously considered by both cosmetics producers and regulators.

KEY WORDS: face cream; homosalate; lip balm; margin of safety; sun-protection products

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